

DISCUSSION ON RIGHT TO CLEAN DRINKING WATER- A BASIC HUMAN RIGHT

Sarvesh Kumar Shahi

Assistant Professor, School of Law, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar; Email id - sarvesh.shahi@kls.ac.in;

Abstract

United Nations General Assembly has, through Resolution no. 64/292 dated July 28, 2010, recognized clean drinking water and sanitation as a basic human right. As a result, several International Organizations and world nations have stepped into strengthening their legal and policy based system to manage the affairs of providing clean water to its citizen. Writing in the Indian context, the present research paper is an investigation of facts relating to efforts made by government and judiciary on giving the level of preference to this pertinent issue of global importance and how they are focusing on supply of clean drinking water and violation of basic human right to access to clean drinking water and sanitation respectively. Further, the research paper highlights the current data of drinking water crisis in few Indian states to drag the attention of readers and policy makers and push the government to re-think and re-plan the drinking water management system in the country which has been given primary importance as a fundamental right by Supreme Court and various high courts from time to time.

Keywords: Water, Human Right, Judiciary, Policy, Law

INTRODUCTION

Access to safe drinking water is a basic human right and an essential foundation of public health, yet many people throughout the world do not have access to these fundamental needs. Safe drinking water, a basic amenity has become a luxury in many Indian households, especially in semi-urban and rural areasⁱ.

The United Nations recognizes the importance of addressing the global water crisis each year on World Water Day, March 22. Globally, 844 million people lack access to clean water. Without clean, easily accessible water, families and communities are locked in poverty for generations. Children drop out of school and parents struggle to make a living. Unsafe drinking water, inadequate availability of water for hygiene, and lack of access to sanitation together contribute to about 88% of deaths from diarrheal diseases.ⁱⁱ

Women and children are worst affected because they are more vulnerable to diseases of dirty water and women and girls because they often bear the burden of carrying water for their families for an estimated 200 million hours each day.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) set ambitious new targets for drinking water, sanitation and hygiene. Target 6.1 under Goal 6 calls for universal access to safe drinking water for all by 2030.ⁱⁱⁱ This target is measured using new global indicators. For example, indicators like proportion of population using safely managed drinking water services, the water should be accessible on premises, the water should be available when needed, the water should be free from contamination. In many low- and middle-income countries, existing water quality data from regulatory authorities is limited, especially for rural areas and populations using non piped supplies. To complement the regulator data, an increasing number of low- and middle-income countries are collecting nationally or sub-nationally representative data on drinking water quality through multi-topic household surveys.

As per Water Aid report published in 2016, India is placed among the worst countries in the world for the number of people without safe water. An estimated 76 million people in India have no access to a safe water supply, and the situation is only getting more serious.

The Asian Development Bank has forecast that by 2030, India will have a water deficit of 50 per cent. The Union Ministry of Water Resources has estimated the country's current water requirements to be around 1100 billion cubic metres per year, which is estimated to be around 1200 billion cubic metres for the year 2025 and 1447 billion cubic metres for the year 2050. Water supply in India has two principal sources, namely water from rivers and groundwater. However, the rivers are shrinking because of pollution and industrialization, while the population keeps growing, pushing us towards an enormous water deficit.

Rampant pollution, dumping of sewage waste and abuse of the rivers has led to large sections of important rivers like Ganga and Yamuna becoming unfit for use of drinking. The Ministry of Jal Shakti is responsible for the development, maintenance and efficient use of water resources in the country and coordination of drinking water and sanitation programs in rural areas. So, it is important to assess the work of the government in providing safe drinking water to the citizens of India. And not only the government but also the role of the higher courts who serves as a protector of fundamental rights of citizen is needed to be assessed.

Further, to begin with, it is pertinent to highlight the constitutional protection to right to water with special reference to discussion on significance of water as a Human/Fundamental right.

WATER AS HUMAN RIGHT

According to the United Nations around 1.2 billion people live in areas of water scarcity, and another 1.6 billion people face economic water shortages.^{iv} In this context, access to water has recently emerged as a human right recognized at the universal level.^v

In 2002, the General Comment No. 15 of the UN committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) set out the right to water as the right of everyone "to sufficient, safe, acceptable, physically accessible and affordable water for personal and domestic uses".^{vi} According to the General Comment, States "have to adopt effective measures to realize, without discrimination, the right to water". Furthermore, in April 2011, the Human Rights Council adopted, through Resolution 16/2, access to safe drinking water and sanitation as a human right: a right to life and to human dignity.^{vii}

Nevertheless people around the globe face up significant difficulties in their access to water. Indeed, the right to water is one of the constitutional guarantees which find many obstacles for its effectiveness both in developing and developed countries.^{viii}

There has been little attention paid as to whether there is a specific human right to water,^{ix} although several attempts have been made in the last 10–15 years to address this right.^x For example, during the drafting of the UN Convention on Non-Navigational Watercourses 1997, a discussion on this issue took place. Unfortunately this caused much disagreement, and no provision regarding the right could be agreed upon. More recently however, the right to water has received more favourable attention and with water being an ever-scarcer resource this is a timely moment for such a development.^{xi}

The right to water has been recognised in a wide range of international human rights documents, including treaties, declarations and other standards,^{xii} although the explicit recognition of water as an individual human right, has yet to take place.

The right to water has been recognised implicitly, that is, under articles that refer to directly related rights contained within the ICESCR 1966, such as an adequate standard of living, food and health.^{xiii}

Despite the lack of explicit wording concerning water, the CESCR has interpreted Article 11 on an Adequate Standard of Living and Article 12 on Health as implicitly including water. It is against this provision that the Committee drafted and adopted the General Comment 15 on the Human Right to Water.^{xiv}

It may also be argued that the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966^{xv} implicitly provides for a right to water under Article 6 (1), the Right to Life.

The two human rights instruments that include explicit provisions concerning the right to water are the

CEDAW and the CRC. CEDAW Article 14 paragraph (2) stipulates that States parties shall ensure to women the right to ‘enjoy adequate living conditions, particularly in relation to water supply^{xvi}. Article 24, paragraph 2, of the CRC requires States parties to combat disease and malnutrition ‘through the provision of adequate nutritious foods and clean drinking-water’. Even though these provisions are the only explicit codifications of the right to water in international human rights treaties, they are far from comprehensive. The CRC’s provision relates only to a certain aspect of water, that of quality (safety). The provision is also framed in relation to the right to health, rather than as an independent right to water.^{xvii}

Despite the explicit wording in both the CRC and the CEDAW, water can thus be viewed as a derivative right. A derivative right is a right deriving from other related or ‘dependent’ rights. For the right to water this would be *inter alia* the right to health, food, housing, education and the right to life^{xviii}. This ill-defined status causes confusion as to the scope and core content of the right to water, thus raising problems concerning its justiciability and implementation. Because of the questioning as to the normative content, it could be difficult to establish whether violations are of the right to water itself or, first and foremost, violations of other related rights. However, as water is a crucial element of the rights provided for in Article 11 of the ICESCR, it can be argued that the right still exists in international human rights law with a ‘unique status’ – somewhere between that of a derivative right and an independent right.^{xix}

Taking into account all these circumstances, the justiciability of the right to water or, in other words, the effective access of citizens to safe water and sanitation is crucial.^{xx}

The enforceability of the right to water and, in general, of Economic, Cultural and Social Rights (ECSR) is a transnational issue which has been raised by prominent scholarship over the past years.^{xxi}

At UN level the efforts undertaken by human rights bodies have resulted in binding and soft law instruments that recognize access to water as a human right. Among them the above mentioned 2002 General Comment No. 15 on the right to water.¹⁶ Even if the Comment has a soft law nature, it defines the parameters to be met in the access to water for personal and domestic uses: accessibility, affordability, accessible and non-discrimination.^{xxii}

The Dublin Conference on Water and Environment in 1992 unfolded a new approach to water resources management, which encouraged privatization of water sector in developing countries. It declared that water has an economic value and must be treated as an economic good. It also stated that access to water and sanitation are fundamental human rights but at affordable prices. The fourth principle of the Dublin Declaration states: “Water has an economic value in all its competing uses and should be recognized as an economic asset. Following this principle, it is especially crucial to recognize the basic right of all human beings to have access to drinking water and sanitation at affordable price. Past failure to recognize the economic value of water led to wastage and to uses that were harmful to the environment. To manage water as an economic asset is an important path to the achievement of efficient and equitable use, and to the encouragement of the conservation and protection of water resources” (Petrella, 2001: 65-66).

In a future scenario of scarcity, the availability of international and national legal mechanisms for redress is critical. In this regard, transnational environmental law is shaping national environmental systems and case law. As a result, the international trend toward the recognition of the right to water is reflected also in national courts^{xxiii}.

After several readings it has been found that defining the scope and core content of the right to water is a difficult task. The core content of right to water covers water for basic needs inclusive of safe and sufficient drinking water and water for food preparation and for hygiene needs. In addition this water must be economically and physically accessible for all in a manner consistent with human dignity.

Special consideration should be taken to ensure this is applied to all vulnerable groups.

India has been a party to all the major international human rights treaties which have accorded a human rights' status to the right to water. An analysis of these conventions arguably leads us to the premise that 'right to water' should be treated as a basic, fundamental and human right even if it is not expressly mentioned in the human rights conventions^{xxiv}.

CONSTITUTIONAL POSITION OF WATER

Constitution of India is a bible of rights and cherished aspersion of people of India. This holy document reflects the promised rights, future governing policy and mechanism to realize and enforce such rights. Numbers of rights have been enumerated in constitution.

In India, the sacred appropriate to access to clean drinking water can be attracted from the privilege to nourishment, the privilege to clean condition and the privilege to wellbeing, all of which have been ensured under the expansive rubric of the Right to Life ensured under Article 21 of the constitution. Notwithstanding article 21, Article 39 (b) of the mandate standards of state arrangement (DPSP), which the Constitution proclaims to be non-justifiable, perceives the guideline of equivalent access to the material assets of the group. Article 39 (b) orders that 'the State should, specifically, coordinate its arrangement towards securing that the proprietorship and control of the material assets of the group are so circulated as best to sub serve the benefit of all.'^{xxv}

Water and related subjects as per the Constitutional scheme is within the purview of the state except in the case of inter-state water disputes. The Constitutional scheme on water is as follows: Water and land are assigned to the state under Article 246 and List II of the Seventh Schedule; water supplies, irrigation and canals, drainage and embankments, water storage and water power under Entry 17 of List II; article 243 G confers authority on the panchayati raj institutions; drinking water and minor irrigation under Eleventh Schedule.

Notwithstanding the Constitutional space for a fundamental right of water, alternate spaces pertinent for water rights and administration are Parts IX and IXA of the Constitution consolidated by the now acclaimed 73rd and 74th Amendments to the Constitution of India that were brought into impact in 1993^{xxvi}. 73rd Amendment of the Constitution had thrown a Constitutional basic on all the state governments to think of a fitting Panchayat Raj Act enumerating meaningful vote based devolution of capacities, functionaries, and assets. In particular, it engages states to enrich panchayats with such powers and expert to empower them to work as foundations of self-government and goes ahead to list 'Drinking Water', 'Water Management', 'Minor Irrigation', and Watershed Development' as subjects under the ward of panchayats.^{xxvii} In a comparative vein, the 74th Amendment to the Constitution of India perceives nearby self administration as an enforceable perfect and obliges the state governments to constitute urban neighbourhood bodies ('ULBs'). Both the 73rd and 74th Amendments to the Constitution motivated changes in the current state level panchayats, metropolitan enterprise and municipal board laws in order to align them with the command under the Constitutional Amendments. It is essential to comprehend these restored state laws in a rights- commitment structure.^{xxviii}

Though 'Water' has been constitutionally dealt with yet there is no fundamental guarantee of right to water as such. It may come as a surprise to many that water - which after air is the most fundamental requirement for human survival - was not till now explicitly recognised as a fundamental human right. This is true of the UN system, and it is true of the Indian legal regime. In both, the recognition of water as a basic right has been indirect, flowing from other rights.^{xxix}

STATUTORY RECOGNITION TO RIGHT TO CLEAN DRINKING WATER

In P.R. Subhash Chandran v. Government of A.P.^{xxx}, the A.P. High court held that "under the constitution,

the role of the State to provide every citizen with adequate clean drinking water and to protect water from getting polluted is not only a fundamental directive principle in the governance of the state but is also a penumbral right under Article 21 of the constitution of India".

In India we find a state legislation, which focuses upon the regulation and control of water resources in the public interest. The legislations are enacted with a single objective of providing and regulating water supply in the state or with a dual objective of water supply in the state and the setting up of corporations or boards for the same.

The water supply legislations are meant for drinking and non-drinking purposes. A broad classification of the water supply laws could be laid down as follows:

- Laws establishing water boards for Urban water supply
- Laws enacted for water supply in metropolitan cities
- Laws for water supply in the state as a whole
- Laws on regulation of groundwater extraction, use and transportation
- Laws on protection of water sources
- Laws for supply of water to specific industrial areas

List of Instruments

- i. Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin) Guidelines (Modified In October 2017)
- ii. Atal Mission for Rejuvenation and Urban Transformation (AMRUT) - Mission Statement & Guidelines, 2015
- iii. Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin), Guidelines for ODF Verification, 2015
- iv. Swachh Bharat Kosh Operational Guidelines, 2014
- v. Guidelines for Swachh Bharat Mission (Urban), 2014
- vi. Guidelines for Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin), 2014
- vii. Indian Standard - Packaged Drinking Water (Other Than Packaged Natural Mineral Water) (BIS IS: 14543), 2014
- viii. Uniform Drinking Water Quality Monitoring Protocol, 2013
- ix. Prohibition Of Employment as Manual Scavengers and Their Rehabilitation Act, 2013
- x. National Rural Drinking Water Programme, (Updated) 2013
- xi. Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and Their Rehabilitation Rules, 2013
- xii. Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan Guidelines, 2012
- xiii. Mgnrega Guidelines (Revised) for Taking up Works Relating to Access to Sanitation Facilities, 2012
- xiv. Guidelines Nirmal Gram Puraskar, 2012
- xv. Bis - Drinking Water Specification, 2012
- xvi. Ensuring Drinking Water Security in Rural India - Strategic Plan 2011-2022
- xvii. Total Sanitation Campaign Guidelines, 2011
- xviii. Rural Sanitation and Hygiene Strategy, 2012 - 2022
- xix. Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission, Revised Guidelines (Sub-Mission for Urban Infrastructure And Governance), 2011
- xx. Guidelines for Engagement of Swachhata Doot, 2011
- xxi. National Rural Drinking Water Programme, 2010
- xxii. Central Pollution Control Board Guidelines for Water Quality Management, 2008
- xxiii. National Urban Sanitation Policy, 2008
- xxiv. Draft Guidelines for Preparation of Legislation for Framing Drinking Water Regulations, 2007

- xxv. Total Sanitation Campaign Guidelines, 2007
- xxvi. Bis Code of Practice for Sanitation With Leaching Pits for Rural Communities, 1988/2007
- xxvii. Guidelines Regarding Constitution of Village Health and Sanitation Committees, 2007
- xxviii. Water Quality Monitoring and Surveillance Programme Guidelines, 2006
- xxix. The Cantonments Act, 2006
- xxx. Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission, Revised Guidelines (Sub-Mission For Urban Infrastructure And Governance), 2006
- xxxi. Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission Guidelines, 2005
- xxxii. Uniform Protocol on Water Quality Monitoring Order, 2005
- xxxiii. Urban Infrastructure Development Scheme for Small and Medium Towns Guidelines, 2005
- xxxiv. Guidelines for Urban Water Sector Reform and Successful Public Private Partnerships, 2004
- xxxv. Model Municipal Law, 2003
- xxxvi. Guidelines on Swajaldhara, 2002
- xxxvii. Water Quality Assessment Authority Order, 2001
- xxxviii. Guidelines for Implementation of Schemes and Projects on Sustainability Under Accelerated Rural Water Supply Programme (Arwsp), 2000
- xxxix. Manual On Water Supply And Treatment, 1999
- xl. Accelerated Rural Water Supply Programme Guidelines, 1999
- xli. Accelerated Urban Water Supply Programme, 1994
- xlii. Employment Of Manual Scavengers and Construction of Dry Latrines (Prohibition) Act, 1993
- xliii. Code of Basic Requirements for Water Supply, Drainage and Sanitation (BIS 1172: 1993)
- xliv. Bureau of Indian Standards Specification For Drinking Water (BIS 10500: 1991)
- xlv. Operational Manual For Water Quality Testing Laboratories, 1990

Thus, The authorities envisaged in the water supply legislations are meant to strengthen the objectives for which the laws are enacted. These laws serve a small section of the Indian population and water supply is in the hands of state agencies. However, any kind of supply of basic utilities constantly reminds us about the need for transparency and accountability. Even the autonomous water boards set up by the states to improve efficiency suffer from political nomination of members and lack of financial autonomy.

CONTEMPORARY ISSUES PERTAINING TO ACCESS TO CLEAN DRINKING WATER

For billions of people worldwide, the poor availability of drinking water restricts consumption patterns and affects quality of life. At present, globally, at least one billion people experience an interruption to their supply throughout a 24 hour period^{xxxix} and around 3.1 billion individuals depend on unreliable, non-piped water supplies that are located off-premises^{xxxix}.

According to the World Health Organization (who) about 884 million people still do not have access to improved sources of drinking-water, 2.6 billion people lack access to improved sanitation^{xxxiii} and there are about 2 million annual deaths attributable to unsafe water and sanitation.^{xxxiv} Further, a new report published by WHO on behalf of UN-Water that reveals that weak government systems and a lack of human resources and funds are jeopardizing the delivery of water and sanitation services in the world's poorest countries – and undermining efforts to ensure health for all^{xxxv}.

The UN-Water Global Assessment and Analysis of Sanitation and Drinking-Water 2019 (known as the GLAAS report) surveyed 115 countries and territories, representing 4.5 billion people. It showed that, in an overwhelming majority of countries, the implementation of water, sanitation and hygiene policies and plans is constrained by inadequate human and financial resources. Nineteen countries and one territory reported a

funding gap of more than 60% between identified needs and available funding. Less than 15% of countries have the financial or human resources needed to implement their plans.

According to the World Economic Forum's 2020 Global Risk Report: there is a high impact risk from "A significant decline in the available quality and quantity of fresh water, resulting in harmful effects on human health and/or economic activity."^{xxxvi}

About half of the countries surveyed have now set drinking-water targets that aim for universal coverage at levels higher than basic services by 2030, for example by addressing water quality and increasing access to water on premises. In addition, specifically targeting open defecation will have a dramatic impact on public and environmental health.

Despite the link that exists between dignity, human rights, drinking water and sanitation, billions of people across the world are unable to effectively realise these rights. The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2018, as prepared by the United Nations Division for Sustainable Development Goals ("SDGs"), reported that in the year 2015, around 29 % (twenty nine per cent) of the world's population lacked safe drinking water supplies, and about 61 % (sixty one per cent) of the world's population lacked sanitation facilities.^{xxxvii} It was also reported that unsafe drinking water and unsafe sanitation continue to be responsible for global mortality. Together, these were responsible for 870,000 deaths in the year 2016. These are disturbing figures since it indicates the unfortunate reality of the continued inaccessibility people face while accessing safe drinking water and sanitation facilities. It indeed remains a bitter pill to swallow knowing that despite advancements being made in the fields of science and technology, which may be used to build robust water conservation and sanitation techniques, a large number of people continue to live in deplorable conditions due to persistent challenges in these sectors.^{xxxviii}

The majority of countries have policies for drinking-water (94%), sanitation (94%), and hygiene (79%) and also reported having implementation plans to support these policies. However, fewer than one sixth of countries with costed implementation plans have sufficient finance to implement them. Of those countries that have conducted human resources assessments, less than 14% have sufficient human resources to implement plans.^{xxxix}

Approximately half of countries have set urban or rural targets to reach 100% coverage for drinking-water at the safely managed or basic levels by 2030.

According the WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme, as of 2017, 2.2 billion people lack safely managed water services, 4.2 billion lack safely managed sanitation and 3 billion lack basic hand-washing facilities.

India is facing the worst water crisis in its history, and 21 Indian cities—including Delhi, Bengaluru, Chennai and Hyderabad—will run out of groundwater by 2020, affecting 100 million people; 40% of India's population will have no access to drinking water by 2030, highlighting the need for "urgent and improved" management of water resources, NITI AAYOG released the report on 'Composite Water Management Index' (CWMI) dated June 14, 2018.

With nearly 600 million Indians facing high-to-extreme water stress – where more than 40 percent of the annually available surface water is used every year – and about 200,000 people dying every year due to inadequate access to safe water, the situation is likely to worsen as the demand for water will exceed the supply by 2050, said the 'Composite Water Management Index' (CWMI) report.

With nearly 70 percent of water contaminated, India ranks 120th of 122 countries in a global water quality index, 2019.^{xi}

The WWF's Risk Filter analysis has projected a bleak scenario for India overall, with almost a third of 100 cities qualify as high-risk zones by 2050. In addition to the two, other 28 cities named by WWF susceptible

to water risk “in the next few decades” are Amritsar, Pune, Srinagar, Kolkata, Bengaluru, Mumbai, Kozhikode, Visakhapatnam, Thane, Vadodara, Rajkot, Kota, Nashik, Ahmedabad, Jabalpur, Hubli-Dharwad, Nagpur, Chandigarh, Ludhiana, Jalandhar, Dhanbad, Bhopal, Gwalior, Surat, Delhi, Aligarh, Lucknow and Kannur.

The survey also assigns a risk score out of five to cities in 2030 and 2050. Anything above three qualifies as ‘high risk’ and above four is ‘very high risk’. All 30 cities have fared poorly on the risk assessment: with each scoring at least a three or more for both 2030 and 2050. At the top are Ludhiana, Chandigarh, Amritsar, and Ahmedabad, with troubling scores of 4.9, 4.8, 4.7, and 4.6 respectively.

Chennai has been devoid of rain for nearly 200 days. In 2018, the city experienced one of its weakest northeast monsoon seasons, which runs from October to December and provides a large portion of the area’s annual rainfall. Additionally, the southwest summer monsoon season from around June through September has been delayed across India and unable to deliver substantial rainfall to Chennai yet.

The future of India’s environment lies in its cities... For cities to break away from the current vicious loop of flooding and water scarcity, nature-based solutions like restoration of urban watersheds and wetlands could offer solutions. This is our chance to re-evolve and re-imagine what the future of the cities could be.

The problem in India isn’t just lack of infrastructure: More than half of India’s districts, a World Bank report says, are threatened by groundwater depletion or contamination. This year, even before summer, almost 33 percent of India is already experiencing droughts or drought-like conditions. The affected areas, mostly in rural India, depend on government water tank trucks to deliver a maximum of 20 to 25 liters of water per person per day—enough for COVID-19 hand washing, but only if the villagers use water for nothing else.

In India, almost 21 percent of communicable diseases, including cholera, dysentery, hepatitis A, and typhoid, are water-borne, and could be prevented in part with better hand washing—as could respiratory diseases such as flu and COVID-19.

The great hope, if the COVID-19 emergency can be said to offer hope, is that it will spur the Indian government to deliver on that promise—and also spur Indians themselves to change their behavior as much as possible, in a way that will bring them lasting benefits after the pandemic passes.

Major Threats - When clean drinking water runs out, people will have no choice but to rely on unsafe water. Disease and illness could run rampant, leading to more deaths and higher infant mortality.

In rural areas, young girls might drop out of school in mass numbers. As the ones traditionally tasked with fetching water, they will need to help their families, and walk much longer distances to rare water access points.

And as the crisis intensifies further, there could be mass migrations to the already overpopulated and under-resourced cities.

GOVERNMENTAL EFFORTS

In her 2020-21 Budget Speech, Finance Minister Ms. Nirmala Sitharaman highlighted the importance of the safe water (Jal Jeevan Mission) and comprehensive sanitation programme (Swachh Bharat Mission) to support the government’s “health vision” and reduce the disease burden among the poor. In the Union Budget 2020-21, the Department of Drinking Water and Sanitation under the Ministry of Jal Shakti has witnessed a slight increase of 17 per cent from the previous year’s allocation. The allocation for the erstwhile National Rural Drinking Water Programme (NRDWP), now called the Jal Jeevan Mission, has been increased by 14.9 per cent in 2020-21 (Budget estimate) compared to the allocation made last year.

Besides providing piped water supply to households that do not have this - around 82 per cent or 146 million households - by 2024, the Jal Jeevan Mission places emphasis on augmenting local water sources, recharging existing sources and reuse of grey water. For this purpose, the slight increase in the allocation may still not be sufficient for implementing the government’s ambitious plan.

Jal Shakti Abhiyan “Jal Shakti Abhiyan (JSA) has delivered over 3.5 lakh water conservation measures in 256 districts. Out of these, 1.54 lakh are of water conservation and rain water harvesting measures, 20,000 relate to the rejuvenation of traditional water bodies, over 65,000 are reuse and recharge structures and 1.23 lakh are watershed development projects.”^{xli}

Rural Sanitation Strategy 2019-2029 Similarly, it is claimed: “The Department of Drinking Water and Sanitation (DDWS), Ministry of Jal Shakti launched the 10 Year Rural Sanitation Strategy (2019-2029), which focus on sustaining the sanitation behaviour change that has been achieved under the Swachh Bharat Mission Grameen (SBM-G), ensuring that no one is left behind, and increasing access to solid and liquid waste management.” The strategy is supposed to ensure “every village has access to solid and liquid waste management.” (Para 10.59) But it’s not clear how this will be achieved.

Moreover, it says: “Swachh Survekshan Grameen 2019 survey covered 17,450 villages in 698 districts across India and include 87,250 public places namely schools, anganwadi centers, public health centres, haat/bazaars/religious places, making it India’s largest rural sanitation survey.” (10.60) But it does not say what did the survey said.

Centre has announced the launch of Nal Se Jal (Water From Tap), a poll-promise from its 2019 manifesto, to ensure piped water to every household by 2024. Reason being In India, only 32 percent of households have tap water supply from treated sources, as per Census 2011. Only seven of India’s states and union territories have tap water supply in over 80 percent households.^{xlii}

JUDICIAL EFFORTS

The Supreme Court and various High Courts have evolved the right to water as constitutional right elevated as fundamental right. The right to ‘pollution free water’ and the right of access to ‘safe drinking water’ has been read as a part of ‘Right to Life’ under Article 21 of the Constitution of India. This has been possible because of a liberal and activist interpretation of the fundamental right to life by the Supreme Court as well as the High Courts of the country in series of cases before them.

Recently, in Delhi Sainik Cooperative Housing Building Society Ltd.(Regd.) and Ors. V. Union of India and Ors.^{xliii}, pronounced on January 11, 2021 the High Court of Delhi sated that “it is settled legal position that right to access to drinking water is fundamental to life and there is a duty of the State under Article 21 of the Constitution to provide clean drinking water to its citizens”.

Earlier, in A.P. Pollution Control Board II vs. Prof.M. V. Nayudu (Retd.) & Ors.,^{xliiv} the Supreme Court held that - Drinking water is of primary importance in any country. In fact, India is a party to the resolution of the UNO passed during the United Nations Water Conference in 1977 as under:

“All people, whatever their stage of development and their social and economic conditions, have the right to have access to drinking water in quantum and of a quality equal to their basic needs.”

Thus, the right to access to drinking water is fundamental to life and there is a duty on the State under Article 21 to provide clean drinking water to its citizens.

Adverting to the above right declared in the aforesaid Resolution, in Narmada Bachao Andolan v. Union of India,^{xliv} Kirpal, J. observed that “Water is the basic need for the survival of human beings and is part of the right to life and human rights as enshrined in Article 21 of the Constitution of India.”

In Hamid Khan V. State of M.P and Ors.,^{xlvi} The Supreme Court observed that “Under Article 47 of the Constitution of India, it is the responsibility of the State to raise the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people and the improvement of public health. It is incumbent on State to improve the health of public providing unpolluted drinking water”. State in present case has failed to discharge its primary responsibility. It is also covered by Article 21 of the Constitution of India and it is the right of the citizens of India to have protection of life, to have pollution free air and pure water.

Similarly, in *Subhash Kumar v. State of Bihar and others*,^{xlvii} the Supreme Court of held that “the right to live includes the right of enjoyment of pollution-free water and air for full enjoyment of life. If anything endangers or impairs that quality of life in derogation of laws, a citizen has right to have recourse to Article 32 of the Constitution for removing the pollution of water or air which may be detrimental to the quality of life”.

Judgments on specific issues

Dealing with specific issues related to drinking water supply and its use, several judgments have been passed to resolve the issues that people in different cities of India are facing.

Listening to the plights of people of Delhi, Supreme Court in *Delhi Water Supply and Sewage Disposal Undertaking v. State of Haryana*,^{xlviii} Apex Court held that “Water is a gift of nature. Human hand cannot be permitted to convert this bounty into a curse, an oppression. The primary use to which the water is put being drinking, it would be mocking the nature to force the people who live on the bank of a river to remain thirsty, whereas others incidentally placed in an advantageous position are allowed to use the water for non-drinking purposes. A river has to flow through some territory; and it would be travesty of justice if the upper-riparian States were to use its water for purposes like irrigation, denying the lower riparian States the benefit of using the water even for quenching the thirst of its residents”.

In a latest judgment of *Delhi Jal Board v. State of Haryana*^{xlix} Regarding increased ammonia levels in river Yamuna due to discharge of pollutants, the 3-judge bench of SA Bobde, CJ and AS Bopanna and V. Ramasubramanian, JJ stated, “It has become necessary, to compare the costs of prevention and control of water pollution against its effects on human health including treatment, indirect economic costs and damage to flora and fauna.” Acknowledging the duties of State to improve the public health of citizens and protect the environment; the Court issued directions to State of Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh, Haryana, Delhi and Uttar Pradesh to submit priority-wise list of Municipalities, river stretches adjacent to which had been found to be most polluted.

CPCB was directed to submit a report identifying municipalities along the river Yamuna, which had not installed total treatment plants for sewage as per the requirement or had gaps in ensuring that the sewage is not discharged untreated into the river. It was also directed to highlight any other source of prominent contamination within the limits of Municipalities.

Despite the Supreme Court's rulings time and again that access to clean drinking water is a fundamental right as part of right to life in Article 21 of the Indian Constitution, the inadequate (or denial of) access to water and sanitation to the poor in India has been going on for a long time even before the advent of economic reforms.¹

CONCLUSION

Thus, International human rights law demands a specific focus on those people who do not fully enjoy their rights, leading to explicitly ‘pro-poor’ development in many countries. It also requires a commitment to progressively reduce inequalities by tackling the discrimination and stigmatization that can lead to people being excluded from, or marginalized in relation to, drinking water and sanitation access.

Although, India is not a water scarce country. But lack of sensitisation with regard to both conservation of water and pollution of water sources has resulted in a large part of the population for whom water has become more of a curse than a boon. Infrastructure for storage of water must be developed properly to ensure that people have access to safe water across the country,

The key is to look at securing drinking water and the role communities play in doing so. Time demands to promote locally owned and managed drinking water security plans which are simple and can be used, monitored and managed by people and local governments, On the other hand, ambitious government projects like the Namami Gange are slowly sowing the seeds of cleanliness on the river front.

Endnotes

- i UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), United Nations Human Settlements Programme(UN-HABITAT), World Health Organization (WHO), *The Right to Water*, Resolution no. 64/292 dated (July 28, 2010).
- ii Robert Bos, Fiona Gore&Jamie Bartram, Safer Water, Better Health: Costs, Benefits and Sustainability of Interventions to Protect and Promote Health, World Health Organization survey, 2008.
- iii Protocol on Water and Health and the 2030 Agenda: a Practical Guide for Joint Implementation, United Nations publication issued by the Economic Commission for Europe, 2019.
- iv United Nations, Water Scarcity. Available at: <http://www.un.org/waterforlifedecade/scarcity.shtml>.
- v Brown Weiss, E., "The Coming Water Crisis: A Common Concern of Humankind" 1(1) *Transnational Environmental Law* 153-168 (2012).
- vi Amanda Cahill, "The Human Right to Water – A Right of Unique Status: The Legal Status And Normative Content of The Right To Water" 9(3) *International Journal of Human Rights* 389-410(2005).
- vii 17 Days of activism for the empowerment of rural women leaders and their communities 1-17 October, 2020 Published by WWSF Women's World Summit Foundation, Geneva.
- viii M. Belén Olmos Giupponi, Martha C. Paz, "The Implementation of the Human Right to Water in Argentina and Colombia" 15 *Anuario Mexicano de Derecho Internacional* 323-352 (2015).
- ix I.J. Alvarez, "The Right to Water as a Human Right", in Piccolotti and Taillent (eds) *Linking Human Rights and the Environment* 2 (US: University of Arizona Press 2003).
- x Noted by E. Riedel, Committee Expert and Rapporteur on the Right to Water for the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Statement on Day of General Discussion, UN CESCR 29th Session, Nov. 2002, Geneva.
- xi Amanda Cahill, "The Human Right to Water – A Right of Unique Status: The Legal Status And Normative Content of The Right To Water" 9(3) *International Journal of Human Rights* 389-410(2005).
- xii For example, ICESCR 1966, CRC 1989 and CEDAW 1979.
- xiii R. P. Hall et al, "The Human Right to Water: The Importance of Domestic and Productive Water Rights" *Sci Eng Ethics* (2014).
- xiv George S. McGraw, "Defining and Defending the Right to Water and Its Minimum Core: Legal Construction and the Role of National Jurisprudence" 8 *Loy. U. Chi. Int'l L. Rev.* 127 (2011).
- xv UN International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966 (hereafter referred to as ICCPR). Adopted 16 Dec. 1966, entry into force 23 March 1976. Ratified by 151 state parties (with 66 signatories) as of 2 Nov. 2003.
- xvi Thorsten Kiefer, Inga Winkler, "Legal Resources for The Right to Water and Sanitation: International and National Standards" – Second edition (2008), Geneva, Switzerland.
- xvii Kaime T, "Children's Rights and the Environment", In Kilkelly U., Liefwaard T. (eds) *International Human Rights of Children. International Human Rights*. (Springer, Singapore, 2018).
- xviii Amanda Jane Cahill, "The Human Right to Water and its Application in the Occupied Palestinian Territories" *ProQuest LLC* (2018).
- xix Ndjodi Ndeunyema, "Unmuddying the Waters: Evaluating the Legal Basis of the Human Right to Water Under Treaty Law, Customary International Law, and the General Principles of Law" 41 *Michigan Journal of International Law* 455(2020).
- xx M. Belén Olmos Giupponi, Martha C. Paz, "The Implementation of the Human Right to Water in Argentina and Colombia" 15 *Anuario Mexicano de Derecho Internacional* 323-352 (2015).
- xxi The IESCR article 20 underlines the obligation of each party "to take steps... to the maximum of its available resources with a view to achieving progressively the full realisation of the rights recognised in the Present Covenant".
- xxii General Comment No. 15 (2002), para. 2.
- xxiii M. Belén Olmos Giupponi, Martha C. Paz, "The Implementation of the Human Right to Water in Argentina and Colombia" 15 *Anuario Mexicano de Derecho Internacional* 323-352 (2015).
- xxiv For example, India has ratified the following treaties: the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1979); the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1979); the Convention on the Rights of Children (1993); the Convention on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women (1993); the Convention Against Torture and other Inhumane or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (1997); the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (1969).
- xxv M. Swathi, R. Dhivya, "Constitutional Perspective of Right to Water in India" 120 (5) *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 3909-3919 (2018).
- xxvi M. Swathi, R. Dhivya, CONSTITUTIONAL PERSPECTIVE OF RIGHT TO WATER IN INDIA, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* Volume 120 No. 5 2018, 3909-3919.
- xxvii <http://savethewater.org/2013/01/06/water-news-article-31-petition-everyone-has-the-right-to-clean-and-accessible-water/>
- xxviii Trishala A., Lakshmi T and Rajeshkumar S, "Physico-Chemical Profile of Acacia Catechu Bark Extract – An In Vitro Study" 3(4) *International Research Journal of Multidisciplinary Science & Technology* 26-30 (April 2018).
- xxix Praveen Patil, "Article 21: A Reservoir of Right to Water?" 4 *Bhatter College Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* 284 (2014).
- xxx 2000 AIR (AP) 272, 2000 (1) ALT 58, 2000 (3) ALD 11, 2000 (2) CPJ 217.
- xxxi Kumpel, E.; Butler, C. CBET-EPSRC: Characterizing the Effects of Supply Hours and Pressure of Intermittent Piped Water Supplies on Water Quality. 2018. Available online: https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/ShowAward?AWD_ID=1804232&HistoricalAwards=false (visited on Jan. 02, 2021).
- xxxii Mackie Jensen, "Measuring Domestic Water Use: A Systematic Review of Methodologies That Measure Unmetered Water Use In Low-Income Settings" 21 *Trop. Med. Int. Health* 1389-1402 (2016).
- xxxiii World Health Organization and unicef, "Progress on Sanitation and Drinking-Water: 201 update", World Health Organization and unicef, at http://whqlibdoc.who.int/publications/2010/9789241563956_eng_full_text.pdf, 2010, pp. 6-7, (visited on Oct. 27, 2012).
- xxxiv World Health Organization. Water Sanitation and Health (wsh), Facts and Figures on Water Quality and Health, at http://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/facts_figures/en/index.html, accessed on 27 September 2011.
- xxxv Un-Water Global Analysis and Assessment of Sanitation And Drinking-Water Glaas 2019 Report.
- xxxvi http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Global_Risk_Report_2020.pdf
- xxxvii United Nations, The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2018, New York 2018, available at <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/files/report/2018/TheSustainableDevelopmentGoalsReport2018-EN.pdf> (visited on Jan. 20, 2021).
- xxxviii Joanna Esteves Mills & Oliver Cumming, "The Impact of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene on Key Health and Social Outcomes: Review of Evidence", published by UNICEF, (June 2016).
- xxxix National Systems To Support Drinking-Water, Sanitation And Hygiene: Global Status Report 2019 Un-Water Global Analysis And Assessment Of Sanitation And Drinking-Water, Glaas 2019 Report.
- xl Global Drinking Water Quality Index Development and Sensitivity Analysis Report Prepared and published by the United Nations Environment Programme, Global Environment Monitoring System (GEMS)/Water Programme, 2019.
- xli Department of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Finance, Government of India, "Economic Survey (2019-20)" (January, 2020).
- xlii TV Jayan, "Jal Jeevan Mission aims to give tap-water to all households by 2024" *The Hindu Business Line*, Oct. 02, 2019.

- xlili W.P.(C) 8364/2018.
xliv (2001) 2 SCC 62.
xlv (2000) 10 SCC 664 : (2000) 7 Scale 34.
xlvi AIR 1997 MP 191, 1997 (1) MPLJ 587.
xlvii A.I.R. 1991 S.C. 420.
xlviii 1996 SCC (2) 572, JT 1996 (6) 107.
xlix. WP(C) No. 8 of 2021, decided on 13-01-2021.
1. Raju Majhi, "Right to Sanitation – a Human Right" 6 *Forensic Research & Criminology International Journal* 535–536 (2018).